

E-marketing and Online Advertising: Case Study in Greek Companies during Economic Crisis

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is the studying of the effects (the impact) on online advertising at the online consumers in the economic crisis of Greek market. The tool for recording and evaluating of the impact between the Online Advertising and online marketing was a closed-ended questionnaire. The information were collected by the use of social media. To extract useful results we have made statistical analysis of collected data, which held at the beginning of Economical year of 2016. We have also implemented appropriate Machine Learning techniques through the use of classification algorithms, clustering and correlation analysis in order to produce inference rules. For the implementation of the Machine Learning techniques we have used the open source software Machine Learning and Data Mining Code R. Two are the basics scopes about that: Firstly, we want to evaluate the significance of exported rules / conclusions and secondly, we want to display the results in a user friendly environment to the final user.

Keywords: Online Advertising, E-Marketing, Social Networks, R, Economic Crisis

1. INTRODUCTION

Global financial community, it has been entered in a new and unknown economic phase. The huge crisis of the financial system, which has been arises in the developed countries results a risk of insolvency and has led to unstable economies and create millions of unemployed worldwide. Today, national economies are closely dependable each other. In addition, commercial and financial information is moving at breakneck speed through the Internet and mobile networks. Today businesses need to be adjusted in an economic environment full of uncertainty, extensive and unpredictable business risks. It requires a strict business operating framework in order to each company to navigate in a financial environment highly unstable. Also businesses need to be able to develop systems, processes and principles, in order to anticipate crises and replace them into opportunities through the fluid situation. In the sense that the economic crisis dramatically changed the behavior of Greek consumers, e-advertising is a promising procedure for marketers to create awareness and influence purchase decision of the undecided consumers. Recently, online advertising have become more aggressive, by using multi methods that consumers. In this paper, we focus on the usage of e-advertising for online purchasing. The aim of this work is to examine the impact of e-advertising on purchasing decision.

1.1. Literature Review

Online advertising and marketing strategies that are based on information bombardment have been are antiquated. Because of the consumer spend more and more time in Internet, the businesses have to rethink how they approach the online marketing. Consumers are not passive receivers of messages. Additional consumers reacts, want to participate, want to create, want to have a share in the product to be consumed.

Online shopping offer flexibility, convenience and fun. Consumers can compare through electronic catalogs and looking at shopping services from the internet. Customers are informed of the products and services that are available any time. On the other side, the interactive marketing has many unique advantages. Initially, businesses can be inspect directly and easily the results of each advertising campaign. The internet offers a very important feature which is named the advantage of «contextual placement». Marketers can buy e- advertisements from sites that are related to their own offerings, as well as to place advertisements based on words related to web search engines, such as Google. In this way, the web is available to consumers when the purchasing process starts. The economic crisis in Greece, which began in 2009 until now, has caused many companies to reduce their budget on traditional marketing activities, leading to a reduction or elimination of corporate

communications with existing or potential customers. Within this climate began to gain ground in e-marketing services, which include the following methods:

- Email Marketing
- Social Media Marketing (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube, Pinterest, κ.λπ.)
- Google Adwords
- Article Marketing
- SEO
- SEM

E-marketing becomes a new reality and it seems that is one of the tip for leading companies out of crisis.

1.2. Psychological Theoretical Framework and e-Marketing

The hierarchy of needs based on Maslow's theory which has been developed in the field of clinical psychology and is used to explain the orientation of human behavior to the needs-motivation, can be an important area of research for the optimization of various techniques of marketing. According to Maslow's theory, there are five levels of human needs, in hierarchical order: (1) Normal (2) Security (3) Love, (4) Assessment and self-assessment and (5) Self-fulfillment or completion. Just needs a level met, the person will go to the next level.

It should be noted that online services of marketing and online advertising products can meet the needs and aspirations in five hierarchical levels. The main reason for the wide acceptance of Maslow's theory is probably, its simplicity. A number of surveys and studies, support the view that consumer behavior in the field of e-marketing and online advertising is geared towards the target. Also incentives affect the nature and volume of the necessary information, and the manner in which such information will be used by targeting the most appropriate choice of the online product, i.e. at the choice that offers the most desired market chances of achieving.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this research paper we use a quantitative research methodology. The process of a quantitative research follows two distinct phases. Firstly, the phase of the design that we mention the objectives of the research and the assumptions may be considered. In the implementation phase is involved in the collection of data, analysis, and the interpretation of results. According to the existing research and the issue of usability we use the questionnaire as a research tool for measuring the impact of online advertising to consumers making online shopping. In this paper a online questionnaire has been completed by consumers through social networks. The purpose of the survey is to assess the impact of online advertising to consumers making online purchases.

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks. Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas. Decision trees, "if-then" rules and neural networks are the most popular such schemas. A lot of algorithms have been proposed in the literature for extracting classification rules from large relational databases, such as symbolic learning algorithms including decision trees algorithms (e.g. C4.5) and rule based algorithms (e.g. CN2), connectionist learning algorithms (e.g. back{propagation networks), instance-based algorithms (e.g. PEELS) and hybrid algorithms. Association rules can be used to represent frequent patterns in data, in the form of dependencies among concepts attributes. In this paper, we consider the special case, that is known as the market basket problem, where concepts-attributes represent products and the initial database is a set of customer purchases (transactions).

3. RESULTS

Classification methods aim to identify the classes from some descriptive traits. They find utility in a wide range of human activities and particularly in automated decision making. Decision trees are a very effective method of supervised learning. It aims is the partition of a dataset into groups as homogeneous as possible in terms of the variable to be predicted. It takes as input a set of classified data, and outputs a tree that resembles to an orientation diagram where each end node (leaf) is a decision (a class) and each non- final node (internal) represents a test. Each leaf represents the decision of belonging to a class of data verifying all tests path from the root to the leaf. The tree is simpler, and technically it seems easy to use. In fact, it is more interesting to get a tree that is adapted to the probabilities of variables to be tested. Mostly balanced tree will be a good result. If a sub-tree can only lead to a unique solution, then all sub-tree can be reduced to the simple conclusion, this simplifies the process and does not change the final result. Ross Quinlan worked on this kind of decision trees.

Decision trees are built in "ctree (Conditional Inference Trees)" by using a set of training data or data sets. At each node of the tree, "ctee" chooses one attribute of the data that most effectively splits its set of samples into subsets enriched in one class or the other. Its criterion is the normalized information gain (difference in entropy) that results from choosing an attribute for splitting the data. The attribute with the highest normalized information gain is chosen to make the decision. During the construction of the decision tree, it is possible to manage data for which some attributes have an unknown value by evaluating the gain or the gain ratio for such an attribute considering only the records for which this attribute is defined. Using a decision tree, it is possible to classify the records that have unknown values by estimating the probabilities of different outcomes. Ctree builds decision trees from a set of training data in the same way as ID3 or C4.5, using the concept of information entropy.

The training data is a set $S = s_1, s_2, \dots$ of already classified samples. Each sample s_i consists of a p-dimensional vector $(x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, \dots, x_{p,i})$, where the x_j represent attribute values or features of the sample, as well as the class in which s_i falls. At each node of the tree, "ctree" chooses the attribute of the data that most effectively splits its set of samples into subsets enriched in one class or the other. The splitting criterion is the normalized information gain (difference in entropy). The attribute with the highest normalized information gain is chosen to make the decision.

The "ctree" algorithm then recurs on the smaller sublists. In order to specify the best result, it was necessary to fit the data to the model in a proper way. This task was carried away by changing and testing the controls of "ctree".

The parameters in the control function that were altered are:

- mincriterion: The value of the test statistic (for testtype == "Teststatistic"), or 1 - p-value (for other values of testtype) that must be exceeded in order to implement a split.
- minsplit: The minimum sum of weights in a node in order to be considered for splitting.
- mtry: The number of input variables randomly sampled as candidates at each node for random forest like algorithms.
- maxdepth: The maximum depth of the tree.

Tree 1

- ✓ Depended variable: sex
- ✓ Independed variables:
 - 'mincriterion' value: 0.0005
 - 'minsplit' value: 10L
 - 'mtry' value: Inf (Infinite)
 - 'maxdepth' value: Inf (Infinite)

Tree 2

- ✓ Depended variable: sex
- ✓ Independed variables: Rest
 - 'mincriterion' value: 0.0005
 - 'minsplit' value: 10L
 - 'mtry' value: Inf (Infinite)
 - 'maxdepth' value: Inf (Infinite)

3.1. Clustering Results

Clustering involves finding a specific number of subgroups (k) within a set of n observations (data points/objects); each described by d attributes. A clustering algorithm generates cluster descriptions and assigns each observation to one cluster (exclusive assignment) or in part to many clusters (partial assignment). Throughout this paper, we shall refer to the output of a clustering algorithm (e.g the medoids of the clusters) as clustering rules. The package "mclust" is for model-based clustering, classification, and density estimation based on finite normal mixture modelling. It provides functions for parameter estimation via the EM algorithm for normal mixture models with a variety of covariance structures, and functions for simulation from these models. Also included are functions that combine model-based hierarchical clustering, EM for mixture estimation and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) in comprehensive strategies for clustering, density estimation and discriminant analysis. Additional functionalities are available for displaying and visualizing fitted models along with clustering, classification, and density estimation results.

*There is also the ability to run the algorithm in order to see how many clusters it finds to be optimal for any case. In our case that number is 4.

(Determination of the optimal model and number of clusters according to the Bayesian Information Criterion for expectation-maximization, initialized by hierarchical clustering for parameterized Gaussian mixture models)

Best BIC values:

EII,4 EII,3 EEE,1

BIC -301.2833 -320.62277 -425.3533

With the use of the BIC value, the algorithm concluded to the following hierarchical clustering model:

Gaussian finite mixture model fitted by EM algorithm

EII (spherical, equal volume) model with 4 component s:

log.likelihood	n	df	BIC	ICL
-113.8003	100	16	-301.2833	-302.5694

Clustering table:

	1	2	3	4
Q6	35	17	17	31

Means:

	[,1]	[,2]	[,3]	[,4]
Q6	2.000000	3	1.000001	1.999999
Q7	1.993436	1	1.000000	1.522597
Q8	2.003388	1	3.000000	2.513325

Plot Interpretation

cluster_bic:

The number of clusters (4) that the algorithm used for the model, and how it ended up using the model (EII) instead of the others with the use of the BIC value.

3.2. Mining Association Rules

Association Rule Mining is a common technique used to find associations between many variables. In Data Mining, Apriori is a classic algorithm for learning association rules. Apriori is designed to operate on databases containing transactions (for example data collected from surveys in this case). As is common in association rule mining, given a set of item sets, the algorithm attempts to find subsets which are common to at least a minimum number C of the itemsets.

Apriori uses a "bottom up" approach, where frequent subsets are extended one item at a time, and groups of candidates are tested against the data. The algorithm terminates when no further successful extensions are found. Apriori uses breadth-first search and a tree structure to count candidate item sets efficiently. It generates candidate item sets of length k from item sets of length k - 1. Then it prunes the candidates which have an infrequent sub pattern. According to the downward closure lemma, the candidate set contains all frequent k-length item sets. After that, it scans the transaction database to determine frequent item sets among the candidates.

Association rules present association or correlation between item sets. An association rule has the form of $A \rightarrow B$, where A and B are two disjoint item sets.

The Goal: studies whether the occurrence of one feature is related to the occurrence of others.

Three most widely used measures for selecting interesting rules are:

- ✓ **Support** is the percentage of cases in the data that contains both A and B,
- ✓ **Confidence** is the percentage of cases containing A that also contain B, and
- ✓ **Lift** is the ratio of confidence to the percentage of cases containing B.

3.3. Apriori rules visualization

• Scatterplot

This visualization method draws a two dimensional scatterplot with different measures of interestingness (parameter "measure") on the axes and a third measure (parameter "shading") is represented by the color of the points. There is a special value for shading called "order" which produces a two-key plot where the color of the points represents the length (order) of the rule.

• Matrix3D

Arranges the association rules as a matrix with the item sets in the antecedents on one axis, and the item sets in the consequent on the other. The interest measure is either visualized by a color (darker means a higher value for the measure) or as the height of a bar (method "matrix3D"). Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

- measure = "lift"
- control = list(reorder = TRUE)

Matrix with 240 rules

Graph for 240 rules

• Grouped Matrix plot

Antecedents (columns) in the matrix are

248

Grouped matrix for 240 rules

grouped using clustering. Groups are represented as balloons in the matrix.

- **Graph**

Represents the rules (or itemsets) as a graph. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

- control=list(type="items")

- **Paracoord**

Parallel coordinate charts are a visualization that consists of N amount of vertical axes, each representing a unique

data set of 82 rules, with lines drawn across the axes. The lines show the relationship between the axes, much like scatter plots, and the patterns that the lines form indicates the relationship. We can also gather details about the relationships between the axes when you see the clustering of lines. Let's take a look at this using the chart below as an example. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

- control=list(reorder=

TRUE)

Apriori rules

For the top 61 rules that were extracted from the apriori the following parameters were altered:

- support: A numeric value for the minimal support of an item set
- confidence: A numeric value for the minimal confidence of rules/association hyperedges

Specifically of our use: Support: 0.8, Confidence: 0.9

After the extraction, the top 10 rules, also, presented lift approximately 1.

id	lhs	rhs	support	confidence	lift
552	{income=[10001-20000],Q8=4}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.14	1.0000000	3.333333
554	{income=[10001-20000],Q7=3}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.14	1.0000000	3.333333
555	{sex=Male,income=[10001-20000]}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.12	1.0000000	3.333333
557	{income=[10001-20000],Q6=4}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.14	1.0000000	3.333333
567	{income=[10001-20000],Q7=2}	=> {age=[43-54]}	0.15	1.0000000	3.225806
568	{education=3,income=[10001-20000]}	=> {age=[43-54]}	0.11	1.0000000	3.225806
570	{income=[10001-20000],Q5=2}	=> {age=[43-54]}	0.15	1.0000000	3.225806
643	{income=[5001-10000],Q4=2}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.16	0.9411765	3.137255
645	{Q4=2,Q8=4}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.16	0.9411765	3.137255
647	{Q4=2,Q7=3}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.16	0.9411765	3.137255
652	{Q4=2,Q6=4}	=> {age=[31-42]}	0.16	0.9411765	3.137255
45	{income=[0-5000]}	=> {age=[18-30]}	0.22	1.0000000	4.166667
451	{Q4=1,Q8=5}	=> {age=[18-30]}	0.16	1.0000000	4.166667
452	{Q5=1,Q8=5}	=> {age=[18-30]}	0.16	1.0000000	4.166667
453	{Q7=3,Q8=5}	=> {age=[18-30]}	0.16	1.0000000	4.166667
455	{sex=Male,Q8=5}	=> {age=[18-30]}	0.12	1.0000000	4.166667
148	{sex=Male,Q4=3}	=> {age=[68+]}	0.13	1.0000000	6.666667
151	{Q4=3,Q6=4}	=> {age=[68+]}	0.15	1.0000000	6.666667
158	{Q7=2,Q8=4}	=> {age=[68+]}	0.15	1.0000000	6.666667

4. CONCLUSION

So in conclusion, one in two online consumers affected markets of the Online ads and conducts online purchases under the influence of online advertising, a large proportion (66%) say unaffected by online advertising, making purchases on the basis of the specific needs and then extensive market research and price comparison (eg skroutz.gr). The consumption habits due to the economic recession in Greece, seems to have changed at high rates. Electronic consumer purchases increased (50%) due to the economic recession in their effort to achieve lower product prices. Businesses looking to advertise online in order to increase their turnover at a rate of 83% while choosing new ways of advertising products and services and approach to consumers. From the above it is concluded that the economic crisis contributed to the further development of e-business.

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